

Spectrophotometric determination of titanium with 2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone benzoyl hydrazone

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Abstract : A simple and sensitive spectrophotometric method for the determination of titanium at trace levels has been worked out using 2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone benzoyl hydrazone as a complexing agent in neutral medium. The complex formed was quantitatively extracted into chloroform with λ_{max} at 371 nm. The method obeys Beer's law in the range 0.0–3.5 $\mu\text{g Ti ml}^{-1}$ having molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity values of $1.35 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 0.0035 $\mu\text{g Ti cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The limit of detection, standard deviation and relative standard deviation of the method are 0.0146 ppm, 0.0012 and 0.276% respectively. The proposed method is highly selective, reproducible and deals with the analysis of a large number of samples to a greater degree of accuracy.

Keywords : Titanium, 2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone benzoyl hydrazone, spectrophotometric determination.

Introduction

Titanium is one of the most abundant elements, widely distributed in the earth's crust, constituent of practically all crystalline rocks. As soils and clays are derived from the crystalline rocks, they also contain titanium, usually as titanium dioxide. Titanium has been detected in sea water. Many plants such as grains, vegetables, trees and shrubs are found to contain metal though in low concentrations. Trace amounts of titanium are also present in all forms of animal life¹. Thus, new analytical methods are in demand for trace analysis of titanium.

Out of a wide variety of reagents employed for spectrophotometric determination of titanium, diantipyryl-methane and thiocyanate², dichlorophenylfluorone³, dibromophenylfluorone⁴, DBN-chlorophosphonazo⁵, 6,7-dihydroxy-2-phenyl-4-carboxylbenzopyrylium chloride⁶, 4-(2-thiazolylazo)-1,2,3-trihydroxy benzene⁷ show high sensitivity, but all these methods call for prior separations from some elements having serious interferences and also are of restricted use because of low Beer's law obedience; whereas, other methods using slippery elm leaf⁸, hydrogen peroxide⁹, 2-(2-thiazolylazo)-*p*-cresol¹⁰,

3,4-dihydroxy benzoic acid¹¹, promethazine hydrochloride and pyrogallol¹² mainly suffer due to lack of sensitivity.

It is also evident from the survey of literature that a large number of methods have been worked out in acid media, whereas there are only a few ones in neutral conditions. So, it is of much interest to develop methods in neutral conditions as is the case at present, while making use of 2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone benzoyl hydrazone as a complexing agent for the metal ion. The proposed method is simple, sensitive and free from the interference of a large number of foreign ions and also handles satisfactorily the analysis of a wide variety of samples including different water samples, soil and pharmaceutical and reverberatory flue dust sample.

Experimental

Reagents :

A stock solution of titanium(IV) containing 1 mg ml⁻¹ was prepared by dissolving an accurately weighed amount of $\text{K}_2[\text{Ti}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2\text{O}]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in minimum volume of dilute

sulphuric acid and made it up to the mark in a 100 ml volumetric flask before standardizing the metal ion gravimetrically¹³. Working solutions at $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ level were made by suitable dilutions therefrom. Similarly, solutions of other metal ions at milligram level were prepared by dissolving their commonly available salts in distilled water or dilute acid.

Chloroform and acetone used were of A.R. grade.

The reagent, 2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone benzoyl hydrazone, 'DHABH' (0.1% m/v), was prepared as under, characterized and dissolved in acetone for use.

Preparation of 2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone benzoyl hydrazone, 'DHABH' :

Equimolar amounts (0.025 mol) of resacetophenone (3.8 g) and benzoylhydrazone (3.4 g) were refluxed for 2 h in ethanol. After cooling the solid mass (DHABH) was filtered out and crystallized from ethanol (m.p. 197 °C).

Samples :

Various sample solutions were obtained by mixing solutions of Ti^{IV} and other metal ions in a suitable proportion.

Reverberatory flue dust : A weighed amount of flue dust from copper manufacturer was mixed with a known amount of titanium and dried in an oven. After fusion of the sample with sodium peroxide (approximately eight times the weight of the sample), the leach was neutralized carefully with conc. H_2SO_4 and finally made alkaline. It was boiled, hydroxide precipitates filtered off, followed by 4–5 washings with distilled water. The filtrate along with the washings was adjusted to contain pH ~ 7 and titanium determined as described below in the procedure.

Water samples : Different water samples from industrial places (sugar mill, thermal power plant and fertilizer plant) at Panipat and religious places (Brahma sarover, Sanhit sarover, Jyotisar sarover) at Kurukshetra (Haryana, India) were collected. Trace amounts of Ti^{IV} were added to these water samples and analyzed to find out titanium present, following the proposed procedure.

Pharmaceutical sample : For determination of titanium, the film coated paracetamol tablet (500 mg), containing titanium was stirred for 10 min in deionized water. The sample solution was quantitatively transferred to a 250 ml volumetric flask, diluted with deionized water to

make it to 250 ml. One ml of this sample is taken for the determination of titanium using the proposed method.

Soil sample : About 1 g of air dried homogenized soil sample was weighed and dissolved in conc. HCl. It was decomposed by heating to dryness on a sand bath. The residue was treated with 20–30 ml of water and the solution thus obtained was filtered into a 100 ml volumetric flask, which is makes up to the mark with deionized water. One ml of this sample is taken for the determination of titanium using the proposed method.

Procedure :

To a sample solution containing $\leq 35 \mu\text{g Ti}^{\text{IV}}$ and/or other metal ions in a 100 ml separatory funnel; added 1.0 ml DHABH (0.1% in acetone) and the aqueous volume was made up to 10 ml with distilled water. The contents were gently mixed and then equilibrated once with an equal volume of chloroform for 30 s. The two phases were allowed to separate and the yellow organic layer was filtered through a Whatman filter paper no. 41 (pre-treated with chloroform) into a 10 ml volumetric flask, which was filled up to the mark with pure chloroform. The absorbance of the reddish brown colored complex was measured at 371 nm against a similarly prepared reagent blank and the amount of titanium was determined from a standard curve obtained by plotting a graph between varying micro amounts of the metal ion and their corresponding absorbance values obtained, as per procedure.

Results and discussion

Absorption spectra :

Ti^{IV} reacted with DHABH forming a reddish brown colored species in neutral medium, which was quantitatively extracted into chloroform. The absorption spectrum of Ti-DHABH complex against blank was determined in the range 350–530 nm. At 350 nm, the absorbance of the complex was 0.202 which increased further and reached a maximum value of 0.282 at 367 nm and remained constant up to 373 nm. Beyond 373 nm the absorbance of the complex was continuously decreasing (Fig. 1). Hence, the absorbance measurements of the system were carried out at 371 nm. The effect of various parameters on the formation and absorbance of the metal complex, while performing a single extraction with 10 ml of chloroform each time, was studied systematically as under :

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of Ti-DHABH complex. Curve A - absorbance of complex measured against reagent blank, Curve B - absorbance of reagent blank measured against pure chloroform. Conditions : $1 \mu\text{g Ti}^{\text{IV}}/\text{ml}$, other conditions are the same as described in the procedure.

Choice of medium :

Using 0.5 ml of all 1 N acids/bases, keeping other experimental conditions the same, in a final 10 ml aqueous volume, the absorbance of complex was found to be maximum at CH_3COOH (0.173); whereas, a negligible absorbance was observed in NaHCO_3 (0.072), Na_2CO_3 (0.036), HCl (0.025), NaOH (0.025), H_3PO_4 (0.016), NH_4OH (0.010), H_2SO_4 (0.008) and HClO_4 (0.004). Hence, neutral medium provides a suitable medium for the system.

Effect of DHABH concentration :

In absence of reagent, the absorbance was nil. A significant rise in absorbance value was noticed on addition of DHABH. It attained a maximum value of 0.282 for 0.8–1.5 ml (Table 1) of the reagent and started decreasing though slowly thereafter. Thus, 1.0 ml DHABH (0.1% m/v in acetone) was appropriate for the system.

Extractant :

The extraction behaviour of the complex with various organic solvents in terms of absorbance was in the order : chloroform > iso-amylalcohol > isobutylmethyl ketone > iso-amylacetate > benzene > xylene > carbontetrachloride > toluene > dichloromethane > 1,2-dichloroethane > diethyl ether. Chloroform was thus chosen as a suitable extractant for the complex.

Equilibration time :

The absorbance of the complex was 0.101 on equilibrating just for 2 s. It was maximum (0.282) and remains unchanged for an equilibration time of 10 s to 2 min. Thus, contact time of 30 s was enough for complete transfer of the complex to the organic phase (Table 1).

Table 1. Effect of various parameters on the absorbance of Ti^{IV} -DHABH complex

DHABH ^a (ml)	0.0	0.5	0.8–1.5	2.0	3.0	4.0
[0.1% (m/v) in acetone]						
Absorbance	0.000	0.242	0.282	0.255	0.220	0.187
Equilibration time ^b (s)	5	10	30	60	120	
Absorbance	0.226	0.282	0.282	0.282	0.282	

Conditions : ^aTi, 10 μg ; aqueous volume = solvent volume = 10 ml; solvent = chloroform; equilibration time = 30 s; $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 371 \text{ nm}$; DHABH (0.1% (m/v) in acetone) = variable. ^bDHABH (0.1%), 1.0 ml; other conditions are the same as in (b) excepting variation in equilibration time.

Stability of the complex :

The metal complex was quite stable more than 8 h with a constant absorbance value of 0.282 at 371 nm. This enables one to carry out safely the absorbance measurements.

Optimum conditions :

For $\leq 35 \mu\text{g Ti}^{\text{IV}}$, 0.8–1.5 ml of DHABH (0.1% m/v in acetone), in a final 10 ml aqueous solution, equilibrating once with an equal volume of chloroform for 30 s, were the optimum conditions for the quantitative transfer of the metal complex to the organic phase, whose absorbance was measured at 371 nm.

Stoichiometry of the complex :

The ratio of Ti to DHABH in the extracted species was determined (in two different sets) using their equimolar solutions $4.177 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ and $1.044 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ respectively at three different wavelengths; 371, 381 and 391 nm by Job's method of continuous variation (Fig. 2). The sharp break in the curves indicates a metal to ligand ratio of 1 : 2 in the extracted species. This was further supported by the mole ratio (Fig. 3) and slope ratio method (Fig. 4a,b).

On the basis of the above studies the most probable structure of the complex is :

Beer's law obedience :

The method obeys Beer's law in the range 0.0–3.5 μg Ti/ml with a molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity values of $1.35 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0035 \mu\text{g Ti cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The limit of detection of the method is 0.0095 ppm calculated by $3S_b/m$ (where S_b is the standard deviation of 10 measurements of the blank and m is the slope of the calibration curve). The standard deviation and relative standard deviation of the method are 0.0007 and 0.248% respectively.

Effect of foreign ions :

The influence of different anions, complexing agents and metal ions on the absorbance of the complex has been investigated under the proposed optimum conditions

Fig. 2. Job's method of continuous variation. Conditions : First set (curve A, B, C), conc. of $\text{Ti}^{\text{IV}} = 1.044 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, conc. of DHABH = $1.044 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, Curve A - 371 nm, Curve B - 381 nm, Curve C - 361 nm. Second set (curve D, E, F), conc. of $\text{Ti}^{\text{IV}} = 4.177 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, conc. of DHABH = $4.177 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, Curve D - 371 nm, Curve E - 381 nm, Curve F - 361 nm.

Fig. 3. Mole ratio method. Conditions : First set (curve A, B, C), conc. of $\text{Ti}^{\text{IV}} = 1.044 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, conc. of DHABH = $1.044 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, Curve A - 434 nm, Curve B - 414 nm, Curve C - 454 nm. Second set (curve D, E, F), conc. of $\text{Ti}^{\text{IV}} = 4.177 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, conc. of DHABH = $4.177 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, Curve D - 434 nm, Curve E - 414 nm, Curve F - 454 nm.

Fig. 4a. Slope ratio method. Conditions : conc. of $\text{Ti}^{\text{IV}} (1.044 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}) = 1 \text{ ml}$, conc. of DHABH ($1.044 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$) = varying, Curve A_1 - 434 nm, Curve B_1 - 414 nm, Curve C_1 - 454 nm.

of the procedure. Chloride (150 mg); ascorbic acid, thio-urea, iodide, thiocyanate (100 mg each); bromide (60 mg each); bromate (50 mg); nitrate (40 mg); nitrite, sulphate (25 mg each); aspirin, sulfosalicylic acid (20 mg each); sulphite, dithionite (2 mg); tartrate (1 mg); were without effect (absorbance was 0.282). EDTA 'disodium salt' (ab-

Fig. 4b. Slope ratio method. Conditions : conc. of Ti^{IV} ($1.044 \times 10^{-3} M$) = varying, conc. of DHABH ($1.044 \times 10^{-3} M$) = 1 ml. Curve A_2 - 434 nm, Curve B_2 - 414 nm, Curve C_2 - 454 nm.

sorbance = 0.042), fluoride (absorbance = 0.192), phosphate (absorbance = 0.188) and oxalate (absorbance = 0.021) (1 mg each); showed the decreased absorbance (Fig. 5).

Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} , Co^{III} , Mg^{II} , Sr^{II} , Ag^I , Nd^{III} , Dy^{III} , Sm^{III} , Na^I , K^I , 10 mg each; Cr^{VI} , Ca^{II} , Re^{VII} , Tl^I , Gd^{III} , Y^{III} , Zn^{II} , Mn^{II} , Eu^{III} , 5 mg each; Au^{III} , Se^{IV} , Ba^{II} , La^{III} ,

Fig. 5. Effect of different anions.

Pr^{III} , 2 mg each; Th^{IV} , Ce^{IV} , Ni^{II} , 1 mg each; Bi^{III} , As^{III} , Os^{VIII} , 0.5 mg each ; Pt^{IV} , Hg^I , Sb^{III} , 0.1 mg each; did not interfere (absorbance was 0.282). Cu^{II} (absorbance = 0.321) and Fe^{III} (absorbance = 0.340) showed high absorbance. To mask Cu^{II} 0.1 mg and Fe^{III} 0.5 mg, 50 mg ascorbic acid was added prior to the addition of reagent (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Effect of different cations. *In presence of 50 mg ascorbic acid.

Applications :

The proposed method was applied successfully for the determination of titanium(IV) in different water samples procured from industrial places (sugar mill, thermal power plant and fertilizer plant) at Panipat and also from religious places (Brahma sarover, Sanhit sarover, Jyotisar sarover) at Kurukshetra (Haryana, India), pharmaceutical sample, soil sample reverberatory flue dust sample from Copper Corporation of India and various synthetic samples (Table 2). The results obtained on applying the proposed procedure for the analysis of soil and pharmaceutical samples besides some other technical samples, are also in excellent agreement with the reference method² compared in terms of their *F*-test and *t*-test values (Table 3).

Table 2. Analysis of different samples by the proposed method

Sr. no.	Sample composition ^a	Ti ^{IV} added (µg)	Ti ^{IV} found (µg) ^b	RSD (%)
1.	Ti ^I (1), Re ^{VII} (1), Cr ^{VI} (1)	15	14.88 ± 0.05	0.30
2.	Ce ^{IV} (0.1), Ti ^I (0.1), V ^V (0.1)	25	24.70 ± 0.05	0.20
3.	Sb ^{III} (2), Cr ^{VI} (2), Pr ^{III} (2)	22	21.71 ± 0.05	0.22
4.	Dy ^{III} (2), Nd ^{III} (2), Re ^{VII} (2)	35	34.49 ± 0.07	0.19
5.	Hg ^I (0.1), V ^V (0.1), Mo ^{VI} (0.1)	18	18.25 ± 0.21	1.18
6.	Y ^{III} (2), Ti ^I (1), Nd ^{III} (1)	11	10.79 ± 0.09	0.89
7.	Gd ^{III} (2), Re ^{VII} (2), Cr ^{VI} (1)	32	32.94 ± 0.24	0.73
8.	Nd ^{III} (2), Sb ^{III} (2), Pr ^{III} (1)	20	19.34 ± 0.14	0.71
9.	Reverberatory flue dust, 50 mg	25	24.05 ± 0.32	1.34
10.	Industrial samples			
	(i) Sugar mill	10.0	9.84 ± 0.14	1.47
		25.0	24.75 ± 0.29	1.16
	(ii) Thermal power plant	10.0	10.34 ± 0.11	1.02
		15.0	14.85 ± 0.27	1.81
	(iii) Fertilizer plant	10.0	9.75 ± 0.18	1.81
		20.0	19.65 ± 0.14	0.74
11	Religious places			
	(i) Brahma sarover	10.0	10.20 ± 0.06	0.62
		15.0	15.80 ± 0.10	0.61
	(ii) Sanhit sarover	10.0	9.25 ± 0.09	1.04
		25.0	23.64 ± 0.24	1.01
	(iii) Jyotisar sarover	10.0	9.85 ± 0.05	0.49
		30.0	29.10 ± 0.27	0.92

^aFigure in parentheses indicates the amount of the metal ion in mg. ^bAverage of triplicate analysis ± standard deviation.

Table 3. Analysis of titanium samples

Sample	Titanium added (µg)	Proposed method		Vojkovic <i>et al.</i> (2004)		<i>F</i> -test ^b	<i>t</i> -test ^c
		Titanium found (µg)	RSD (%)	Titanium found (µg)	RSD (%)		
Soil	–	2.27 ± 0.04	1.75	2.21 ± 0.03	1.26	2.03	2.34
	5.0	7.26 ± 0.07	1.03	7.23 ± 0.06	0.76	1.86	0.68
Pharmaceutical	–	6.16 ± 0.02	0.30	6.18 ± 0.03	0.40	0.48	1.67
	5.0	11.13 ± 0.09	0.80	11.17 ± 0.07	0.60	1.69	0.66
Ba (33), S (20) ^d	11.5	11.54 ± 0.06	0.48	11.60 ± 0.03	0.24	3.81	1.94
Mg (8), Al (1), Fe ^{III} (6), B (4) ^e	10.0	9.94 ± 0.03	0.30	9.98 ± 0.03	0.34	0.79	1.68
La (1), Le (0.5), Y (1), V (1), Fe ^{II} (4) ^f	9.65	9.64 ± 0.05	0.57	9.67 ± 0.07	0.70	0.66	0.81
Nb (5), Fe ^{II} (3) ^g	9.00	8.96 ± 0.07	0.78	8.92 ± 0.08	0.89	0.79	0.81

^aMean ± standard deviation (*n* = 4). ^bTabulated *F*-value for (3,3) degree of freedom at 95% confidence limit is 9.28. ^c Tabulated *t*-value for 6 degree of freedom at 95% confidence limit is 2.447. ^dSample is analogous to Benitotite. ^eSample is analogous to Warwickite and in presence of 10 mg of ascorbic acid. ^fSample is analogous to Irispite and in presence of 10 mg of ascorbic acid. ^gSample is analogous to Dicksbergite and in presence of 10 mg of ascorbic acid.

Table 4. Comparison of the proposed method of determination of titanium(IV) with some of the existing methods

Sl. no.	Aqueous conditions	(i) λ_{\max} (nm) (ii) Beer's law range ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	Molar absorptivity ($\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	Interfering metal ions	Ref.
1.	Ti ^{IV} , HCl (0.05 M), slippery elm leaf	(i) 415 nm (ii) 0.2–6.0	0.68×10^4	Fe ^{III} , Zr ^{IV} , Mo ^{VI}	8
2.	Ti ^{IV} , H ₂ SO ₄ , hydrogen peroxide	(i) 410 nm (ii) 3.2–60.0	0.73×10^3	?	9
3.	Ti ^{IV} , pH 2.0–2.6, CALX-S6	(i) 403 nm (ii) 0.0–4.8	1.02×10^4	Mn ^{II} , Ce ^{III} , Zr ^{IV}	15
4.	Ti ^{IV} , azopyrazolone	(i) 520 nm (ii) –	5.0×10^3	?	16
5.	Ti ^{IV} , 3,4-dihydroxy benzoic acid	(i) 380 nm (ii) 0.0–3.0	1.43×10^4	?	11
6.	Ti ^{IV} , NaHCO ₃ (0.035 M), DHABH	(i) 434 nm (ii) 0.0–4.0	1.51×10^4	Fe ^{III} , Cu ^{II} (24 metal ions are non-interfering)	Proposed method

Conclusion

The method worked out for the spectrophotometric determination of titanium(IV) in different water samples, pharmaceutical, soil, reverberatory flue dust and various synthetic samples is simple, highly selective and sensitive, with good reproducibility. Further, the proposed method compares favorably well with the existing methods especially in respect of molar absorptivity and interferences (Table 4).

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